

Cost Analysis of Compressive Sensing for MIMO STAP Random Arrays

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Abstract—This work proposes an augmented variation of conventional space-time adaptive processing (STAP), and explores the application of multi-branch matching pursuit (MBMP) to a multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) beamformer whose steering vector is created over an array having random, inter-element spacing. By applying compressive sensing (CS), a radar system is able to minimize the undesired effects of an undersampled array while providing adequate clutter suppression and reduced burden on array integration. In this paper, we compare the performance and computational complexity of the MBMP applied to the STAP problem and the STAP beamformer. In addition we propose two methods to reduce the computational complexity of MBMP, a modification to the MBMP algorithm which we refer to as truncated MBMP, and a grid refinement technique. We evaluate our approach and extend this aspect to help in understanding the necessary computations required for practical target detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that a filled array (i.e., uniform array with half wavelength or denser element spacing) ensures the absence of grating lobe in the visible region of the array pattern. Critically sampling the array bodes well in the beamforming stages of target detection by space-time adaptive processing (STAP). In contrast, a sparse array is highly prone to aliasing, and depending on the inter-element spacing, is likely to incur significant sidelobes. It has been shown that sparse random arrays exhibit identical spatial resolution with fewer receive elements than a uniform linear array (ULA) of similar size [4]. To aid the increased DoF requirement for random arrays, a multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) random array architecture has been studied [2], [3], [11]. A MIMO random array places both transmit antennas and receive antennas along the array randomly. The effect of using M transmitters and N receivers in this fashion allows one to make MN measurements and increases the number of DoF available.

Even with the increased DoF from a MIMO random array, high sidelobes are an unavoidable characteristic. As such, random arrays require additional signal processing to accurately estimate target location [5]. Compressive sensing (CS) techniques tailored for sparse localization frameworks may offer a means to compensate for the cost of additional DoF, while allowing the radar system designer to benefit from the reduced integration burden associated with random arrays [6]-[8]. In particular, an interesting link was made that shows that compressive sensing can cope with the spatial undersampling

of the MIMO random array [2], [3] and reap the full benefits of a large undersampled array.

Although advances such as CS has shown improvements in performance compared to the conventional STAP beamformer [6], [16], [18], little has been done to show its practicality in terms of computational complexity. In this paper, we compare the performance and computational complexity of both compressive sensing to STAP and the STAP beamformer. We also discuss methods to reduce the computational complexity of CS in STAP, for practical use. To solve the compressive sensing problem, we use the multi-branch matching pursuit (MBMP) algorithm [3], which is an algorithm in the family of matching pursuit (MP) algorithms. We chose the MBMP to solve the CS problem because MP algorithms are greedy algorithms and often require lower computational complexity. The MBMP algorithm in addition offers a way to trade off complexity and performance [3].

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: the signal model is found in Section II; a review and analysis on the computational complexity of the STAP beamformer and STAP with MBMP is presented in Section III; methods to reduce the computational complexity for the MBMP are introduced in Section IV; numerical results are presented in Section V; Section VI contains a short discussion on additional methods to reduce the computational load; conclusions can be found in Section VII.

II. SIGNAL MODEL

Consider a MIMO radar system mounted on an aircraft, in which N elements collect echoes from M transmitters, each transmitter transmits a finite train of L -pulse coherent waveforms sent with a pulse-repetition-interval T_r . It is assumed that the M waveforms are orthogonal to each other. The radar operating carrier wavelength is λ , and the airborne platform velocity is v_p , where the velocity vector is assumed aligned with the array axis. The N receive sensor positions are assumed to be given by the sequence $\mathbf{Z} = [z_1, z_2, \dots, z_N]$, similarly the positions of the M transmitters are assumed to be given by the sequence $\mathbf{T} = [t_1, t_2, \dots, t_M]$. Let the aperture size of the receive array and the transmit array be given by Z_{rx} and Z_{tx} respectively, then the size of the array is defined by $Z = Z_{tx} + Z_{rx}$. In this paper we consider a MIMO random

array where the positions of receive and transmit elements are distributed across the array according to the uniform random variables $U \sim [0, Z_{rx}]$ and $U \sim [0, Z_{tx}]$.

Let $u = \sin \phi$ denote the spatial frequency associated with azimuth angle measured with respect to the normal to the array. The $N \times 1$ receive steering vector $\mathbf{c}(u)$, which represents the baseband response of the N receive sensors to a target at spatial frequency u , is given by

$$\mathbf{c}(u) = [e^{j2\pi z_1 u}, e^{j2\pi z_2 u}, \dots, e^{j2\pi z_N u}]^T. \quad (1)$$

Similarly, the $M \times 1$ transmit steering vector $\mathbf{b}(u)$, which represents the response of the target at spatial frequency u , by the M transmitters is given by

$$\mathbf{b}(u) = [e^{j2\pi t_1 u}, e^{j2\pi t_2 u}, \dots, e^{j2\pi t_M u}]^T. \quad (2)$$

From (1) and (2), we define the $MN \times 1$ spatial steering vector $\mathbf{d}(u)$,

$$\mathbf{d}(u) = \mathbf{b}(u) \otimes \mathbf{c}(u) \quad (3)$$

where \otimes is the Kronecker product. We also define the $L \times 1$ temporal steering vector $\mathbf{v}(f)$ for a target with Doppler frequency f

$$\mathbf{v}(f) = [1, e^{j2\pi f T_r}, \dots, e^{j2\pi(L-1)f T_r}]^T. \quad (4)$$

Then the $MNL \times 1$ space-time steering vector is given by

$$\mathbf{a}(u, f) = \mathbf{v}(f) \otimes \mathbf{d}(u). \quad (5)$$

Finally, the $MNL \times 1$ received baseband signal \mathbf{y} at the array from a target at spatial frequency u , Doppler frequency f and with complex amplitude x is given by

$$\mathbf{y} = x\mathbf{a}(u, f) + \mathbf{n}. \quad (6)$$

In the later sections of this paper, we apply optimization algorithms that operate on a grid. To this end, we discretize the angle-Doppler map into $G = \bar{G}^2$ grid points, where \bar{G} is the number of grid points in each of the two domains. Then, the $MNL \times 1$ lowpass equivalent signal \mathbf{y} received at the array from K targets, with $G \gg K$, is given by

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n}. \quad (7)$$

Here, $\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{a}(u_1, f_1) \mathbf{a}(u_1, f_2) \dots \mathbf{a}(u_{\bar{G}}, f_{\bar{G}})]$ is an $MNL \times G$ matrix of steering vectors associated with possible target locations on the angle-Doppler map, \mathbf{x} is a $G \times 1$ vector of target gains that is sparse in the sense that it has $K \ll G$ non-zero rows. Finally, \mathbf{n} is an interference vector that may consist of ground clutter and thermal noise.

It is common practice to treat the ground clutter and thermal noise as uncorrelated processes. The $MNL \times MNL$ interference covariance matrix \mathbf{R} is given by

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{n}\mathbf{n}^H] = \mathbf{R}_c + \mathbf{R}_n \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{R}_n is the covariance matrix of the thermal noise given by $\mathbf{R}_n = \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}$, and \mathbf{R}_c is the covariance matrix of the ground

clutter. A typical model for the covariance matrix of the ground clutter [10] is

$$\mathbf{R}_c = \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} s_i \mathbf{a}(u_i, f_i(u)) \mathbf{a}^H(u_i, f_i(u)) \quad (9)$$

where the superscript H denotes the conjugate transpose operator, N_c is the number of clutter scatterers, s_i is the power of the clutter scatterer at spatial frequency u_i with the normalized Doppler frequency $f_i(u) = \beta u$ where $\beta = 4v_p T_r / \lambda$.

III. COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY

In this section is analyzed the computational complexity of two competing methods of target detection: traditional STAP and compressive sensing based MBMP.

A. Conventional STAP Beamformer

In this section, we briefly review the STAP beamformer and its computational complexity. The complexity of STAP will serve as a benchmark for comparison with compressive sensing based methods. The STAP beamformer digitally steers an array for all points on an angle-Doppler map, and calculates the output of the array for each point. The output of the array $p(u, f)$ for an angle-Doppler pair (u, f) , is given by the equation

$$p(u, f) = \mathbf{w}^H(u, f) \mathbf{y} \quad (10)$$

where the STAP weight vector is given by

$$\mathbf{w}(u, f) = \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{a}(u, f) \quad (11)$$

The term \mathbf{R}^{-1} in (11) plays the role of canceling as much of the unwanted clutter contributions in \mathbf{y} as possible. The clutter contributions in \mathbf{y} need to be suppressed to ensure that slow moving targets are not masked by clutter.

The number of operations required to calculate (10) for a single beamformed point is $\mathcal{O}(MNL)$ operations. Therefore, to generate the output in (10) for all angle-Doppler combinations, a total of $\mathcal{O}(MNLG)$ operations are required. Each output is compared to a threshold value γ , and a target is detected when $p(u, f) \geq \gamma$, where γ is a threshold set by false alarm considerations.

B. Compressive Sensing in STAP

In this section we review CS, its application to the STAP problem and its computational complexity. In particular, we will focus our attention to the multi-branch matching pursuit (MBMP) algorithm and compare it to the STAP beamformer.

Compressive sensing aims to solve the following problem

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\mathbf{x}} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}\|_2^2 \\ & \text{subject to } \|\mathbf{x}\|_0 \leq K. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\|\bar{\mathbf{x}}\|_0$ represents the number of non-zeros in $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$, $\bar{\mathbf{y}}$ is the measurement vector, and \mathbf{A} is dictionary matrix. To apply this framework to the STAP problem, we note that \mathbf{y} contains significant contributions from clutter. Since we are interested in detecting targets not clutter, the latter has to be removed

from the data. To that end, the received data is whitened by the application of the whitening transformation $\mathbf{R}^{-1/2}$. The signal model for the whitened data is given by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{y}} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{e} \quad (13)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{y}} = \mathbf{R}^{-1/2}\mathbf{y}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{R}^{-1/2}\mathbf{A}$ and $\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{R}^{-1/2}\mathbf{n}$. Note that the noise \mathbf{e} is white. The optimization problem for the whitened data is:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{x}} \|\tilde{\mathbf{y}} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{x}\|_2^2 \\ \text{subject to } \|\mathbf{x}\|_0 \leq K. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The $\|\mathbf{x}\|_0$ constraint in (14) however is non-convex and results in a NP-hard problem, which is impractical to solve.

There exists a rich literature of approximate solutions to (14). Two common approaches are basis pursuit (BP) (e.g. [12]) and matching pursuit (MP) (e.g. [13], [3]) algorithms. BP converts the non-convex problem into a convex problem, and hence achieves a global solution. However, it often requires tuning of parameters and typically more computation time than MP based algorithms. In this work is adopted an MP-based approach to solve (14).

In MP applied to the STAP problem, one starts by initializing an empty support S . Subsequently, the algorithm searches for the steering vector in $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}(\bar{u}, \bar{f})$ that maximizes the metric defined by the inner product between $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}(u, f)$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}$. The column index of $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}(\bar{u}, \bar{f})$ is then added to S then computes the orthogonal projection of the S columns of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$, denoted as $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_S$ using the following

$$\Pi_S = \mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_S \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_S^\dagger \quad (15)$$

where \dagger is the pseudoinverse operator. The algorithm then searches for the next steering vector that maximizes the inner product of $\Pi_S \tilde{\mathbf{a}}(u, f)$ and $\Pi_S \tilde{\mathbf{y}}$ the column vector's index is then added to S and the process is repeated until K elements are in S .

The MP pursuit algorithm summarized above only takes the steering vector that achieves the largest metric, the MBMP algorithm [3] generalizes this concept by allowing the considerations of steering vectors that do not maximize the metric. In essence MBMP allows us to try more combinations of steering vectors at the cost of additional computational complexity.

Next, we briefly review the MBMP algorithm. It is first instructive to reformulate (14) in terms of the support S

$$\begin{aligned} \min_S \|\Pi_S \tilde{\mathbf{y}}\|_2^2 \\ \text{subject to } |S| \leq K. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Problem (16) is equivalent to (14) in the sense that given the optimal solution S_{opt} we can find the optimal $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ by $\tilde{\mathbf{x}} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{S_{opt}}^\dagger \tilde{\mathbf{y}}$.

The MBMP algorithm can be thought of generating a tree of nodes as shown in Fig 1. Each node in the tree is populated with a support such that the node's level indicates the cardinality of

Fig. 1. Example of the MBMP algorithm with $\mathbf{d} = [2, 2]$

its associated support e.g., all nodes at level 2 contain supports with $|S| = 2$. The algorithm terminates when all nodes at level K have been populated, and the support that minimizes $\|\Pi_S \tilde{\mathbf{y}}\|_2^2$ is chosen as the estimate of the support. The structure of the tree is defined by a vector \mathbf{d} , where the number of levels in the tree is defined by the length of \mathbf{d} . The number of children at level k for each node at the $k - 1$ level generates is given by d_k .

For the STAP problem, the support of the nodes are chosen in the following way. First, a node at level 0 is initialized with an empty support. The algorithm then searches for the d_1 steering vectors of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ with the d_1 largest metrics defined by the inner product between $\tilde{\mathbf{a}}(u, f)$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}$. Each node is populated with a support S that corresponds to one of the d_1 steering vectors of $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$. After all the d_1 nodes are populated, the first level is complete, and the algorithm moves on to populate all the nodes at level 2. Each of the d_1 nodes searches for the d_2 columns that maximize the inner product $\Pi_S \tilde{\mathbf{a}}(u, f)$ and $\Pi_S \tilde{\mathbf{y}}$. Each node at level 1 then creates d_2 children nodes, each of the children nodes are populated with a support S that corresponds to one of the d_2 steering vectors and the support of the parent. After all the nodes in level 2 are populated, the algorithm moves on to populate the nodes at level 3. The algorithm stops when it populates all the nodes at level K . The algorithm then outputs all the nodes generated and their associated support.

We now discuss the computational complexity of implementing the MBMP algorithm. We first define D , the total number of nodes, $D = \sum_{i=1}^K \prod_{j=1}^i d_j$. Then from [3], the complexity of the MBMP is $\mathcal{O}(MNL D G)$. Therefore the cost of applying the MBMP algorithm is D times more than the conventional beamformer. In the simplest case, each level has a single node, $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{1}_K$, where $\mathbf{1}_K$ is a vector of all ones. Then the complexity of the MBMP algorithm is $\mathcal{O}(MNL K G)$. In Section V, are shown numerical examples that demonstrate performance trade offs associated with the choice of the number of branches \mathbf{d} .

At first glance the MBMP seems very promising, being only D times more complex than the STAP beamformer. Unfortunately, the above discussion is valid if the number of targets K is known apriori. This is an assumption that simply does not hold in radar applications, as the number of targets cannot be known beforehand. To overcome this, [2] suggested the use of an upper bound on the number of targets \bar{K} . Then, again, in the simplest case when we consider $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{1}_{\bar{K}}$, which corresponds to the structure of a single branch entering and leaving each level, the complexity of estimating target locations is $\mathcal{O}(MNL \bar{K} G)$.

However, because \bar{K} was assumed to be an upper bound, false targets are necessarily included if $K < \bar{K}$. Therefore the output of the MBMP algorithm (all the supports) is sent to another algorithm, where targets are detected. From [2], the test statistic is given by

$$T_i(\tilde{\mathbf{y}}, S) = \frac{(MNL - |S|)|\mathbf{x}_i|^2}{\|\Pi_S \tilde{\mathbf{y}}\|_2^2 [\mathbf{A}_S^H \mathbf{A}_S]_{i,i}^{-1}} \geq \gamma_{CS} \quad (17)$$

where, S is the support associated with the node, γ_{CS} is a threshold parameter, and i is the column index that was added to that node. This statistic is first applied to the supports in every node at level \bar{K} (the last level). If any of the supports passes the test, the algorithm outputs that support. If the supports of every node at level \bar{K} fails the test (17), all nodes at level \bar{K} are removed from the tree, and the $\bar{K} - 1$ level is tested. This test continues until a node passes the test statistic or every node is removed from the tree. From hereon, we refer to this algorithm (MBMP plus the algorithm that performs target detection) as *MBMP-STAP*.

Calculating the matrix inversion in (17) for a single node requires $\mathcal{O}((MNL)^3)$ operations. In the worst case the algorithm has to apply the statistic for all D nodes, therefore the upper bound on the complexity of this algorithm is $\mathcal{O}((MNL)^3 D)$. The larger \bar{K} is, the more that (17) must be computed for a given γ_{CS} . If \bar{K} is much larger than K , computing this test statistic can be quite costly due to the matrix inversion in (17). In the next section, we discuss methods to reduce the complexity of MBMP-STAP, so we could reap the benefits of compressive sensing methods without prohibitive computational complexity.

IV. REDUCING COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY

From the previous section, the computational complexity of running MBMP-STAP with the upper bound on the number of targets \bar{K} and $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{1}_{\bar{K}}$ is $\mathcal{O}(MNL\bar{K}G)$. Then, for a given radar system (fixed N, M, L), the MBMP-STAP algorithm has two parameters that may be changed to lower computational complexity: \bar{K} and G . In this section, we discuss two reduced complexity methods: (1) a truncated version of MBMP-STAP targeting \bar{K} and referred to as *truncated MBMP-STAP*, and (2) a *grid-refined MBMP-STAP* that reduces the size of the grid G .

A. Truncated MBMP-STAP

From (16), it can be seen that the optimal S contains \bar{K} elements, since due to the noise, overestimating S reduces the objective function. To reduce the computational cost, we reformulate (16) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \min |S| \\ & \text{subject to } \|\Pi_S \tilde{\mathbf{y}}\|_2^2 \leq \epsilon \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where ϵ is a design parameter. To solve (18), the truncated MBMP-STAP starts in the same fashion as the MBMP-STAP algorithm, by initializing the node at level 0 with an empty support, and then populating nodes at level 1. When all the

nodes at level 1 are populated, the algorithm tests whether any of the nodes meets $\|\Pi_S \tilde{\mathbf{y}}\|_2^2 \leq \epsilon$. If at least one node does, then the algorithm terminates, and the node with the smallest $\|\Pi_S \tilde{\mathbf{y}}\|_2^2$ is returned as the solution. Otherwise, the algorithm moves on to populate all the nodes at level 2, then does another test to determine whether to terminate the operation when all the nodes in level 2 have been populated. This process repeats until the test terminates the algorithm or until all the steering vectors are added to S .

To choose the value of ϵ we follow the approach used by [9] to obtain a value of ϵ such that the probability of $\|\mathbf{e}\|_2^2 \geq \epsilon$ is small. Assuming that the transformed noise \mathbf{e} is complex white Gaussian and is independent and identically distributed it approximately has a χ^2 distribution with MNL degrees of freedom for reasonable SNR. The value of ϵ can then be chosen to achieve a desired confidence interval from the χ^2 cumulative distribution function with MNL degrees of freedom. For additional details we refer the reader to [9].

B. Grid-Refined MBMP-STAP

To reduce the number of grid points, we apply a grid refinement technique similar to that in [9]. The motivation behind grid refinement is intuitive: if the number of grid points G is chosen such that the grid spacing matches the requirement for target's location accuracy δ , and if δ is small, then G becomes large. Instead, the grid-refined starts with a coarse grid with spacing $\delta_0 > \delta$, which generates a grid of $G_0 < G$ points. The MBMP-STAP or the truncated MBMP-STAP algorithms are run with this coarse grid to obtain an initial estimate of target locations. The grid is then refined locally for the grid points that correspond to target locations. Assume that \tilde{K} target locations were chosen, and let (u_0, f_0) be a grid point where a target was detected. Then, all angle-Doppler pairs corresponding to spatial frequencies $[u_0 - \delta_0, u_0 - \frac{\delta_0}{2}, u_0, u_0 + \frac{\delta_0}{2}, u_0 + \delta_0]$ and Doppler frequencies $[f_0 - \delta_0, f_0 - \frac{\delta_0}{2}, f_0, f_0 + \frac{\delta_0}{2}, f_0 + \delta_0]$ are used to form a new grid. Note that the new grid has 24 points around each of the points of the original grid. This process is repeated for all \tilde{K} grid points, and the remaining grid points that do not correspond to targets are discarded. At each step of the refinement, the new grid has a spacing half of the previous one. This process may be repeated Q times, until $\delta_Q \leq \delta$.

For the i -th iteration, $i \geq 1$ ($i = 0$ corresponds to the initial estimate) a maximum of $G_i = 25\tilde{K}$ grid points due to the grid refinement generating 25 grid points for each target. A significant complexity reduction ensues, since at each grid iteration, the complexity is $\mathcal{O}(MNL D G_i)$, and $G_i \ll G$. As this process is repeated Q times, the grid-refined MBMP-STAP algorithm has complexity of $\mathcal{O}(MNL D G_m Q)$, where G_m is $\max(G_1, G_2, \dots, G_Q)$.

V. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In this section, numerical examples are presented to compare the performance and computational complexity of the STAP beamformer, truncated MBMP-STAP and grid-refined MBMP-STAP. For all algorithms, the number of receive elements

$N = 3$, transmit elements $M = 3$, number of temporal points $L = 10$, the array length $Z = 10\lambda$, signal to noise ratio (SNR) = 20 dB, and clutter to signal ratio (CSR) = 15 dB. The N receive sensors and M transmitters are distributed along the array according to a uniform distribution. The realization of the array is fixed throughout the experiments. For the truncated MBMP-STAP, the detection threshold ϵ was set to 0.62, such that the probability of the noise power exceeding the threshold (false alarm), $\|\mathbf{e}\|_2^2 \geq \epsilon$, is about 1%, the MBMP-STAP algorithm set $\bar{K} = 30$. Unless specified otherwise, the structure of the tree for the MBMP-STAP algorithm is defined by a single node at each level, i.e. $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{1}_{\bar{K}}$.

For MBMP-STAP and truncated MBMP-STAP, grid refinement is employed and the final grid spacing between two adjacent spatial frequencies u is set to $\delta = 0.005$, unless stated otherwise. The final grid spacing between two adjacent normalized Dopplers f is also set to $\delta = 0.005$. The initial grid spacing between any two adjacent spatial frequencies or any two adjacent normalized Dopplers is $\delta_0 = 0.05$ unless stated otherwise. For a target at (u, f) and estimate at (\hat{u}, \hat{f}) , the MSE per target is defined as $\text{MSE} = (u - \hat{u})^2 + (f - \hat{f})^2$. The aggregate MSE for all targets is the sum of all MSEs. For figures concerning the probability of detection, a target is considered detected correctly if the $\text{MSE} \leq 0.0025$, which corresponds to a maximum error of about 0.03 in both the spatial frequency and normalized Doppler domain.

To illustrate the performance with grid refinement, Fig. 2 shows the MSE as a function of the final grid spacing. The target locations are chosen in the following way: every experiment, the targets are assigned the spatial frequencies $u_1 = 0.57$ and $u_2 = 0.5$, then every experiment we draw from a uniform distribution $U \sim [-0.01, 0.01]$ and add the value that was drawn to both u_1 and u_2 . Similarly, every experiment the target Dopplers are assigned the Doppler $f_1 = f_2 = 0$, then another value is drawn from a uniform distribution $U \sim [-0.01, 0.01]$ and the value drawn is added to f_1 and f_2 . This procedure is done to ensure that the targets are not on a grid point. As expected, the MSE for both MBMP-STAP and truncated MBMP-STAP both decrease as the grid spacing becomes finer, however at around $\delta_{grid} = 0.025$ the MSE no longer decreases and using a finer grid doesn't offer any improvements in MSE.

Fig. 3 shows the receiver operating curves (ROC) for the STAP beamformer, MBMP-STAP and truncated MBMP-STAP for four targets. Similar to Fig. 2, for every experiment, the targets are assigned the spatial frequencies $u_1 = 0.57$, $u_2 = 0.5$, $u_3 = -0.7$ and $u_4 = -0.75$ then, every experiment we draw from a uniform distribution $U \sim [-0.01, 0.01]$ and add the value that was drawn to u_1 , u_2 , u_3 and u_4 . Similarly, every experiment the target Dopplers are assigned the Doppler $f_1 = 0$, $f_2 = 0$, $f_3 = 0.5$ and $f_4 = 0.5$ then another value is drawn from a uniform distribution $U \sim [-0.01, 0.01]$ and the value drawn is added to f_1 and f_2 . From the figure, we can see a large performance gain using the MBMP-STAP or the truncated MBMP-STAP. We also notice that the truncated MBMP-STAP performs nearly identical to the MBMP-STAP.

Fig. 2. MSE vs desired accuracy δ , of two targets. The targets are separated by 0.07 in spatial frequency. SNR = 20 dB, CSR = 15 dB.

Fig. 3. ROC curve for STAP Beamformer, MBMP-STAP and truncated MBMP-STAP for four targets. SNR = 20 dB, CSR = 15 dB.

Fig. 4 shows the probability of detection versus target separation in spatial frequency for two targets for the STAP beamformer, truncated MBMP-STAP, and truncated MBMP-STAP with $\mathbf{d} = [3, 3, 3, 1, 1, \dots, 1]$. To control the probability of detection, the threshold parameters γ and γ_{CS} was set to $\gamma = 60$ and $\gamma_{CS} = 100$, it was found that these thresholds achieved a probability of detection of 0.9 when the targets were separated in u by 0.07. The STAP beamformer suffers in performance for two targets that are closer than 0.07 in u , while truncated MBMP-STAP performs well. As expected, we can see a higher probability of detection with a tree with a higher number of branches $\mathbf{d} = [3, 3, 3, 1, 1, \dots, 1]$.

Fig. 5 shows the computational time spent running STAP beamformer, MBMP-STAP, truncated MBMP-STAP, and truncated MBMP-STAP with $\mathbf{d} = [3, 3, 3, 1, 1, \dots, 1]$ for different initial grid spacings δ_0 . Grid refinement was used on all the curves except the STAP beamformer, which used the spacing, $\delta_0 = 0.01$. It was found that the grid spacing $\delta_0 = 0.01$, for the STAP beamformer achieved the same performance as that in Fig. 4 for targets separated by 0.07 in u . Comparing MBMP-STAP and truncated MBMP-STAP we see that our truncated version spends about a quarter of the time that the MBMP-STAP would, and requires slightly more computation time than the STAP beamformer. The truncated MBMP-STAP curve with $\mathbf{d} = [3, 3, 3, 1, 1, \dots, 1]$ is more expensive computation wise

Fig. 4. Probability of detection vs target separation of two targets for STAP beamformer, MBMP-STAP, truncated MBMP-STAP, and truncated MBMP-STAP with $\mathbf{d} = [3, 3, 3, 1, 1, \dots]$. SNR = 20 dB, CSR = 15 dB

Fig. 5. Time vs initial grid size δ_0 for STAP beamformer, MBMP-STAP, truncated MBMP-STAP, and truncated MBMP-STAP with $\mathbf{d} = [3, 3, 3, 1, 1, \dots]$. SNR = 20 dB, CSR = 15 dB

but allows us to achieve better performance as seen in Fig. 4.

VI. DISCUSSIONS

In addition to the methods used in this paper, to reduce the computational complexity, one may also consider methods that reduce the dimensionality of the problem. This not only reduces the computation time required to solve the methods in this paper, but may also reduce the number of samples needed to estimate the covariance matrix. The most common, direct method is the use of a cell averaging constant false-alarm rate (CACFAR) radar [19], where one uses a subset of the space-time snapshots for estimating the range cell under test. Additional methods for reducing the dimensionality can be found in [20].

In practice, the interference covariance matrix \mathbf{R} is not available and must be estimated from training data. From [10] one can obtain an estimate $\hat{\mathbf{R}}$ via sample matrix inversion using $2MNL$ training data samples. To reduce the required number of training data samples, rank reduced methods [15], [14] have been studied which was shown to require $2(NM + L)$ training data.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the performance and complexity of the STAP beamformer and MBMP-STAP was compared for a random

MIMO array. We demonstrate that although the MBMP-STAP is more computationally expensive compared to the STAP beamformer it provides significantly higher performance than the STAP beamformer. In addition we showed that modifying the MBMP-STAP to the truncated MBMP-STAP, and using a grid-refinement strategy we can reduce the computational complexity greatly. It was also shown that since the MBMP algorithm allows the user to trade off a more computationally expensive system for higher performance.

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